

A Modified Preference-Based Hypervolume Indicator for Interactive Evolutionary Multiobjective Optimization Methods: Supplementary Materials

MaoMao Liang¹^e

¹*Faculty of Information Technology, University of Jyväskylä, P.O. Box 35 (Agora), Jyväskylä, Finland*
{maomao.m.liang, babooshka.b.shavazipour, bhupinder.s.saini, michael.t.m.emmerich, kaisa.miettinen}@jyu.fi

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Abstract: Various interactive evolutionary multiobjective optimization methods have been proposed in the literature for problems with multiple, conflicting objective functions. In these methods, a decision maker, who is a domain expert, iteratively provides preference information to guide the optimization process while gaining insight into the problem. To compare interactive evolutionary multiobjective optimization methods, a preference-based hypervolume indicator (PHI) has been proposed to quantify the performance of the methods. PHI was the first indicator designed based on some desirable properties of indicators for interactive evolutionary multiobjective optimization methods. However, it has some shortcomings, such as excluding some potentially interesting solutions and being limited only to a single type of information. In this paper, a modified indicator called PHI⁺ is proposed to address the drawbacks mentioned above. PHI⁺ modifies the region of interest in PHI. Whereas PHI requires the decision maker to supply preference information in the form of a reference point, PHI⁺ is capable of accommodating methods that utilize desired ranges of objective functions as preference information. Therefore, PHI⁺ is the first indicator designed to evaluate interactive methods using two types of preference information. The experimental results show that PHI⁺ can also better distinguish differences in the performance of interactive evolutionary methods.

1 NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

In this section, we illustrate the functionality of PHI⁺ in assessing interactive methods. The interactive methods chosen for comparison include an Interactive RVEA (Hakanen et al., 2016), referred to as IRVEA in this paper, and an IOPIS algorithm (Saini et al., 2020). This IOPIS algorithm allows users to combine preference information with any evolutionary algorithm into an interactive algorithm, the version we use is IOPIS/RVEA which uses RVEA as the underlying evolutionary algorithm, similar to IRVEA. We choose these two interactive methods because their source code can be found in the DESDEO framework (Misitano et al., 2021)—an open source

framework for interactive multiobjective optimization problems. The source code of PHI⁺ is available at <https://github.com/emmerichmtm/phiplus>.

1.1 Test Problems

Four problems from REal world problem (RE) suite (Tanabe and Ishibuchi, 2020), namely RE2-3-2, RE3-4-2, RE3-5-4, RE6-3-1, are selected as the test problems in our experiments, because they are built on real-world problems, have different properties, such as continuous or mixed variables, and they are computationally cheap. Referring to the feasible solution obtained by pre-running before the experiment and the experiment in Aghaei Pour et al. (2024), the optimization process is divided into two phases, the first four iterations are in the learning phase, and the last two iterations are in the decision phase.

For fair comparison, we set the same number of generations in each iteration for both algorithms. To get results quickly, we set the number of generations

^a <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-8567-8236>

^b <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6516-4423>

^c <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2455-3008>

^d <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7342-2090>

^e <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1013-4689>

to 1 for the problem with 2 objective functions since we use it only to show how PHI^+ works and to avoid all solutions converging to one location, while for other problems we set the number of generations to 100. To make it more likely to obtain a feasible solution, we set the population size to 1000 for the problems with 6 objective functions and to 100 for the other problems. Since the ideal and nadir points of problems are provided in Tanabe and Ishibuchi (2020), a normalization step is performed before calculating the PHI^+ value to improve its accuracy. The dystopian point for PHI in each problem is set to the corresponding nadir point.

1.2 Optimization Process of RE2-3-2

To visually compare the differences between the way PHI and PHI^+ work, we graphically show how they are calculated on a test problem with two objective functions in Figure 1. In the visualization of this process, the ROI for PHI is represented by the area surrounded by blue lines, the solutions that dominate r are in the square surrounded by blue solid lines (Figure 1 (a)), and the solutions dominated by r are in the square surrounded by blue dashed lines. The modified ROI for PHI^+ is indicated by the area enclosed by the blue line, excluding the gray grid area (Figure 1 (c)).

Naturally, the preferences depend on the solutions of the previous iteration. For compactness, we list them as follows:

a) Iteration 1: The DM sets desirable ranges, we derive $r = (25, 12.5)$ and the deviations on objective functions are 25 and 12.5 from there. The DM express the initial preference to understand what types of solutions may exist.

b) Iteration 2: The DM wants to learn more about functions, and sets desirable ranges from which we derive $r = (160, 10)$ and the deviations on objective functions are 25 and 12.5. Based on the solutions found in Iteration 1, the DM sets the preference information to see more solutions in the ROI.

c) Iteration 3: The DM sets new desirable ranges that correspond to $r = (20, 100)$ and the deviations on objective functions are 25 and 12.5, to study more the first objective function. The DM is interested in learning about different parts of the PF. Therefore, based on the solutions seen in Iteration 2, they provide new preference information to see more solutions in the new ROI.

d) Iteration 4: The DM sets desirable ranges leading to $r = (10, 5)$ the deviations on objective functions are 10 and 5, expecting to see lower values on objective functions. Same as Iteration 3, the DM is interested in seeing more solutions in a different part

of the PF.

e) Iteration 5: The DM provides desirable ranges to see if the solutions obtained meet their expectations, and we get $r = (30, 5)$ and the deviations on objective functions are 10 and 5. In the previous iteration, the DM has found the region that they are most interested in. They set the new preference information to focus more in the same (and nearby) region and find more solutions of interest.

f) Iteration 6: The DM sets desirable ranges corresponding to $r = (5.9, 0)$ and the deviations on objective functions are 10 and 5, expecting to see lower values on objective functions. The DM found that their preferences were pessimistic and easily achieved in Iteration 5. They provide new preference information based on the knowledge gained to find more desirable solutions.

Iteration	1	2	3
PHI	1.093990076	1.461817041	1.55402991
PHI⁺	3.104009333	12.48452761	13.512463
Iteration	4	5	6
PHI	1.02790275	1.082717159	0.995462552
PHI⁺	2.182101576	5.779339391	0.176329054

Table 1: The PHI and PHI^+ values of IRVEA on RE2-3-2

To demonstrate the difference between PHI and PHI^+ in different cases, we observe their performance in the 5th and 6th iterations. In the 5th iteration, when r is attainable, as shown in Figure 1 (a), the PHI value is $(1 + A1/(A1 + A2))$, that is, one plus the green area divided by the sum of the white and green areas. As shown in Figure 1 (c), the PHI^+ value is $(A3 + A4)/A4$, that is, the sum of the green and gray grid areas divided by the gray grid area.

In Figure 1 (a), since z^d is far away from r , all solutions appear to be close to r . To clearly show the distance between them, we enlarge a part of Figure 1 (a) and show the partially enlarged image in Figure 1 (b). As shown in Figure 1 (b) and 1 (c), there is a solution that is close to r and incomparable to r , it may provide information of interest to the DM. This solution is in the modified ROI for PHI^+ but not in the ROI for PHI , and it is evaluated in PHI^+ but not evaluated in PHI . Therefore, it can be seen that PHI^+ can more accurately represent the performance of the method under evaluation.

In the 5th iteration in Table 1, the PHI value is 1.082717159, and the PHI^+ value is 5.779339391. When r is attainable, the PHI value is limited to $[1, 2]$, the PHI^+ value ranges from 1 to infinity. Therefore, the PHI^+ value can more clearly show the differences in the performance between the methods under evaluation than the PHI value.

In the 6th iteration, when r is unattainable, as

Figure 1: Pareto optimal solutions obtained by IRVEA on RE2-3-2

shown in Figure 1 (d), the PHI value is $(A1/(A1 + A2))$, that is, the green area divided by the sum of the white and green areas. As shown in Figure 1 (f), the PHI⁺ value is $A3/(A3 + A4)$, that is, the green area divided by the sum of the white and green areas. To clearly show the distance between solutions, we enlarge a part of Figure 1 (d) and show the partially enlarged image in Figure 1 (e). As shown in Figure 1 (e) and 1 (f), there is a solution that is far away from r and dominated by r , the DM may not be interested in this solution. This solution is not in the modified ROI for PHI⁺ but in the ROI for PHI, and it is not evaluated in PHI⁺ but evaluated in PHI. Therefore, PHI⁺ can more accurately represent the performance of the method under evaluation.

In the 6th iteration in Table 1, the PHI value is 0.995462552 and the PHI⁺ value is 0.176329054. When r is unattainable, PHI will obtain a good value as long as there is a solution close to r on any objective. Therefore, it is impossible to know whether there is a solution in the ROI through PHI values. PHI⁺ will obtain a good value only when the solutions within the modified ROI are diverse and convergent. We can directly understand the performance of the method being evaluated through PHI⁺ values.

1.3 Further Investigation

To observe the performance of PHI⁺ on problems with different objective functions, we test it on problems RE3-4-2, RE3-5-4 and RE6-3-1. Referring to

the experiment in Aghaei Pour et al. (2024), we compare PHI⁺ values with PMOD (Hou et al., 2018), EH (Bandaru and Smedberg, 2019), R-HV (Li et al., 2017) and PHI values to verify the effectiveness of PHI⁺. Similarly to the idea in Section 1.2, the desirable range in each iteration is set by the preference information provided in Table 2 for the problems.

First, we conduct the experiment on RE3-4-2, a problem with 3 objective functions and 4 decision variables. From Table 3, it can be seen that the comparison results obtained by PHI⁺ are consistent with the those of most indicators in each iteration, that is, overall IOPIS outperforms IRVEA. In the 2nd iteration, the comparison result obtained by PHI⁺ is consistent with those of EH and R-HV, while PHI is consistent only with PMOD. In other words, the results of PHI⁺ are consistent with those of most other indicators, while PHI is inconsistent. This may be because some solutions that may be of interest to DM and incomparable to r are in the modified ROI for PHI⁺, but not in the ROI for PHI. This results in a difference between PHI and PHI⁺ due to variations in the solutions chosen for evaluation. In some cases, R-HV and PHI⁺ values may be 0 since there is a trimming step in R-HV that removes solutions outside its ROI, while in PHI⁺, only the HV value of solutions in the modified ROI is considered. In this way, solutions that may be of interest to DM will not be included in an ROI and will not lead to deviations in the indicator value.

Observing the changes in the indicator values during the optimization process in RE3-4-2 in Figure 2 (a), it can be seen that the difference in performance

RE3-4-2	Reference point	The deviation on each objective
1	(12.5, 11000, 22500)	5, 2000, 5000
2	(2, 5000, 10000)	5, 2000, 5000
3	(5, 3000, 5000)	5, 2000, 5000
4	(1, 10, 20)	0.05, 1, 1
5	(0.5, 5, 10)	0.05, 1, 1
6	(0.1, 1, 2)	0.05, 1, 1
RE3-5-4	Reference point	The deviation on each objective
1	(1690, 10, 0.26)	60, 10, 0.6
2	(1680, 8, 0.26)	60, 10, 0.6
3	(1670, 8, 0.26)	60, 10, 0.6
4	(1668, 10, 0.2)	16, 5, 0.2
5	(1665, 9, 0.1)	16, 5, 0.2
6	(1663, 7, 0.05)	16, 5, 0.2
RE6-3-1	Reference point	The deviation on each objective
1	(80000, 500, 2500000, 6000000, 80000, 2)	20000, 400, 1000000, 1000000, 20000, 2
2	(75000, 300, 2000000, 5000000, 70000, 1.5)	20000, 400, 1000000, 1000000, 20000, 2
3	(70000, 200, 1500000, 4000000, 60000, 1)	20000, 400, 1000000, 1000000, 20000, 2
4	(69000, 150, 1400000, 3000000, 60000, 1)	20000, 300, 1000000, 500000, 20000, 1
5	(68000, 100, 1300000, 2000000, 60000, 1)	20000, 300, 1000000, 500000, 20000, 1
6	(66000, 50, 1200000, 1000000, 50000, 0.5)	20000, 300, 1000000, 500000, 20000, 1

Table 2: Preference information provided in each iteration

between the two methods is very small, and it is difficult to intuitively select a better method. This is because the PHI value is restricted to $[0, 2]$. When r is attainable, the denominator of PHI depends on the method under evaluation (see (??)), so the denominators are different for different methods, and we cannot directly know the difference in the performance of the compared methods through PHI values. Unlike PHI, the denominator of PHI^+ is the same when r is attainable. Thus, the performance differences of the compared methods can be directly understood through PHI^+ values. From Figure 2 (b), it can be clearly seen, overall, IOPIS performs better than IRVEA.

Then, we conduct the experiment on RE3-5-4, a problem with 3 objective functions and 5 decision variables. From Table 4, it can be seen that the comparison results obtained by PHI^+ are consistent with the results obtained by most indicators in most iterations. In the 2nd, 3rd and 5th iteration, the comparison result obtained by PHI^+ is not consistent with those of PHI, this may be because some solutions that may be of interest to DM and incomparable to r are in the modified ROI for PHI^+ , but not in the ROI for PHI. In the 4th and 5th iteration, the comparison result obtained by PHI^+ is not consistent with those of EH and R-HV. This may be because the ROIs for EH and R-HV are based on the closet point. Some solutions that are not close to the closet point but close to the r may be of interest to DM, and these solutions will be included in the modified ROI but not in the ROI based on the closet point, which may lead to deviations in the indicator values.

Observing the changes in the indicator values during the optimization process in RE3-5-4 in Figure 3

(a) PHI values during optimization process

(b) PHI^+ values during optimization process

Figure 2: Indicator values for IRVEA (blue line) and IOPIS (red line) in each generation on RE3-4-2. The arrow \uparrow means the higher the indicator value, the better the performance of the interactive method.

(a), it can be seen that the difference in performance between the two methods is small in the first 500 iterations, it is difficult to select the better method according to this figure. From Figure 3 (b), it can be clearly seen that the performance of the two methods is quite different in the first 500 iterations. Overall, IRVEA performs better than IOPIS.

Then, we conduct the experiment on RE6-3-1, a problem with 6 objective functions and 3 decision

Iteration		PMOD ↓	EH ↑	R-HV ↑	PHI ↑	PHI ⁺ ↑
1	IOPIS	154.4071937	1999.98648	1676.38172	1.68090319	486.5876263
	IRVEA	1.129085216	10000	1521.934097	1.679170466	475.2927316
2	IOPIS	227.9023075	9999.995991	61.21082769	1.316852089	52.22377589
	IRVEA	25.03773653	1479.857017	50.14056541	1.31691891	50.21494727
3	IOPIS	87.72181979	4999.921529	330.271601	1.276944821	35.15850448
	IRVEA	48.55757423	1673.55525	290.1309632	1.273241991	34.17108906
4	IOPIS	3.452903605	10.00702665	22.07726517	1.02187581	23403.98376
	IRVEA	9.035303629	36.61519267	18.65678749	1.017959046	22590.961
5	IOPIS	3.331378448	10	12.40537031	1.008559623	2141.756218
	IRVEA	0.484197089	5	9.999852948	1.004397147	1551.2086
6	IOPIS	3.614060778	2	1.330848817	0.997803096	0
	IRVEA	0.440644425	1	5.210310633	0.992931125	0

Table 3: Comparison of indicator values of IRVEA and IOPIS on RE3-4-2

Iteration		PMOD ↓	EH ↑	R-HV ↑	PHI ↑	PHI ⁺ ↑
1	IOPIS	835.453029	12.64496059	10.22316437	1.99918798	4.515854079
	IRVEA	92.51838298	4.362603774	10.3072547	1.999278501	4.859604436
2	IOPIS	1673.861231	7.421106053	8.622651362	1.966617898	1.837725023
	IRVEA	138.622376	4.75108238	10.14611427	1.932706535	3.01134949
3	IOPIS	1667.265546	3.097226292	9.467710465	1.973480249	1.632014283
	IRVEA	119.0052179	3.106871368	10.15044883	1.934855518	2.359472076
4	IOPIS	1663.658541	6.083685904	9.584802895	1.917112019	6.715731896
	IRVEA	111.1759261	1.925725174	9.472857926	1.937629448	7.678010907
5	IOPIS	1662.407058	3.291969819	8.355476064	1.45264741	2.330869621
	IRVEA	61.71655598	1.197269414	8.191976506	1.418980345	2.489341326
6	IOPIS	1665.505518	1.374736165	0.244449937	0.563753066	0.046177122
	IRVEA	72.47897237	1.969633235	2.187187958	0.776882835	0.079654754

Table 4: Comparison of indicator values of IRVEA and IOPIS on RE3-5-4

variables. From Table 5, it can be found that the comparison results obtained by PHI^+ are consistent with those of most indicators in each iteration. In the 3rd and 4th iterations, the comparison result obtained by PHI^+ is consistent with those of EH and R-HV, while PHI is consistent only with PMOD. In other words, the result of PHI^+ is consistent with those of most other indicators, while PHI is inconsistent. This may be because as the number of objective functions increases, the number of solutions that are incomparable to r increases, and the possibility of the existence of solutions that are incomparable to r and close to r increases. These solutions are evaluated in PHI^+ , but are not evaluated in PHI. As can be seen in Figure 4 (a), IOPIS significantly outperforms IRVEA based on PHI. In Figure 4 (b), in general, IOPIS outperforms IRVEA, but in some generations between iterations 0 to 100 and 300 to 400, IRVEA outperforms IOPIS.

REFERENCES

Aghaei Pour, P., Bandaru, S., Afsar, B., Emmerich, M., and Miettinen, K. (2024). A performance indicator for interactive evolutionary multiobjective optimization methods. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, 28(3):778–787.

Bandaru, S. and Smedberg, H. (2019). A parameterless performance metric for reference-point based multi-

objective evolutionary algorithms. In *Proceedings of the Genetic and Evolutionary Computation Conference*, pages 499–506.

Hakanen, J., Chugh, T., Sindhya, K., Jin, Y., and Miettinen, K. (2016). Connections of reference vectors and different types of preference information in interactive multiobjective evolutionary algorithms. In *2016 IEEE Symposium Series on Computational Intelligence (SSCI)*, pages 1–8. IEEE.

Hou, Z., Yang, S., Zou, J., Zheng, J., Yu, G., and Ruan, G. (2018). A performance indicator for reference-point-based multiobjective evolutionary optimization. In *2018 IEEE Symposium Series on Computational Intelligence (SSCI)*, pages 1571–1578. IEEE.

Li, K., Deb, K., and Yao, X. (2017). R-metric: Evaluating the performance of preference-based evolutionary multiobjective optimization using reference points. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, 22(6):821–835.

Misitano, G., Saini, B. S., Afsar, B., Shavazipour, s., and Miettinen, K. (2021). DESDEO: The modular and open source framework for interactive multiobjective optimization. *IEEE Access*, 9:148277–148295.

Saini, B. S., Hakanen, J., and Miettinen, K. (2020). A new paradigm in interactive evolutionary multiobjective optimization. In *International Conference on Parallel Problem Solving from Nature*, pages 243–256. Springer.

Tanabe, R. and Ishibuchi, H. (2020). An easy-to-use real-world multi-objective optimization problem suite. *Applied Soft Computing*, 89:106078.

Iteration		PMOD ↓	EH ↑	R-HV ↑	PHI ↑	PHI ⁺ ↑
1	IOPIS	69023.33973	1017227.977	4021.224407	1.999959471	5640.662396
	IRVEA	331441.6631	1305203	116.4456705	1.08363764	588.4267904
2	IOPIS	31883.52311	859053.4263	1838.265625	1.993434299	1289.311626
	IRVEA	329367.8325	1280993.084	0	0.874824083	0
3	IOPIS	49990.21765	518626.659	308.2535891	1.891161929	131.7795327
	IRVEA	327916.186	1257083.879	729	1.750252643	177.6926426
4	IOPIS	109689.4638	321812.029	280.9769895	1.802623792	117.0497472
	IRVEA	337053.2617	1060884.8	729	1.650671667	233.0279756
5	IOPIS	370974.5311	59664.2039	93.2395735	1.487178401	9.287837855
	IRVEA	402900.4772	772683.1252	0	0.99687993	0
6	IOPIS	283023.3339	83602.32013	0	0.762739479	0
	IRVEA	601745.0918	933278.7646	0	0.477177905	0

Table 5: Comparison of indicator values of IRVEA and IOPIS on RE6-3-1

(a) PHI values during optimization process

(b) PHI⁺ values during optimization process

(a) PHI values during optimization process

(b) PHI⁺ values during optimization process

Figure 3: Indicator values for IRVEA (blue line) and IOPIS (red line) in each generation on RE3-5-4. The arrow ↑ means the higher the indicator value, the better the performance of the interactive method.

Figure 4: Indicator values for IRVEA (blue line) and IOPIS (red line) in each generation on RE6-3-1. The arrow ↑ means the higher the indicator value, the better the performance of the interactive method.